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Fostering Inclusivity and Cultural Sensitivity: The Role of Institutions in a Diverse World

The key to having a more inclusive and culturally sensitive learning environment is through the initiatives of each educational institution. As each school has their own way of achieving our common and shared goal and that is to offer the best learning experience to our dear clients-the students where barriers are being removed and diversity is being promoted.

One of the ways that an institution could foster is through the enhancement with the admission policy where all the students will be admitted regardless of their race, socio-economic status, gender, culture, or learner with disabilities. As I am currently connected in a higher education institution, our institution practices no discrimination when it comes to accepting students. In this way, all the students will feel that they are given the freedom to be part of the institution that they want to attend.

The notion above is supported by R.A no. 7277 or also known as Magna Carta for Disabled persons where in the provision stated in chapter 2- Education section 12 where it emphasized that admission policy should be enhance that could cater all type of learners including those with disabilities and they should be denied from it as everyone has an equal right (National Council on Disability Affairs, n.d.). Moreover, in the book chapter of Weller (2023) he shared that in China, they shifted their admission policy into a more inclusive one as they aid the diversity of the students for marginalized groups for a fairer education. This practices on the inclusive admission policy is also being implemented in India as revealed by Dey and Bika (2023) that the said country has progressive policies aiming to improve equal opportunity especially for those who has special needs.

On the other hand, another way that an institution could foster a culturally sensitive environment is through recognizing the different cultural backgrounds and practices of each learner. With this, the integration in the curriculum about Indigenous People education is one of the initiatives that an institution could do to foster sensitivity when it comes to culture among all learners. To share with you, in the institution that I am currently connected with, we did a curriculum revision where we integrated an institutional subject solely created for the purposes of introducing the different IP communities in our Region. Through this, it fosters cultural sensitivity as the students will learn the differences between culture and its respective importance. This is supported by Mehta (2024) who stated that a culturally responsive curriculum integrates that promotion of cultural background that paved the way for academic success as it fills the gaps on the cultural differences among the students.

Another way for the educational institution to foster inclusivity is to see to it that the facilities and learning environment consider students with disabilities. How can a student

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learn if the environment is the one that hampers their learning? In this sense, the environment of the institutions served as the one who promotes access of this learner and if the facilities are not accessible. Then, we could generalize that certain institutions give so much weight on considering easy access to facilities among learners with disabilities. Ramps and handrails as well as schedule modification could really foster inclusivity. In this way, learners with disabilities will feel that they are being valued- a key to acceptance. This problem is also being encountered in Ethiopian Public Universities where Muzemil (2018) where he revealed that buildings such as classrooms are not PWD-ready. Aside from that, there are poor ramps that are not accessible for learners with disabilities. The claim on the importance of accessibility is reflected in R.A. 7277 section 25, where a barrier-free environment is being emphasized (National Council on Disability Affairs, n.d.). With this, Mokobane (2024) recommends that teachers need to create an inclusive learning environment where learners with special needs will feel that they are being valued and accepted.

Indeed, educational institutions could help instilling inclusivity and cultural sensitivity through various means. Let's always remember to take part as an educator in promoting inclusion in our classroom. With this, we could have an amazing world where every child feels that they are being accepted and valued.

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